

Effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among the high school adolescent girls in selected schools of Damoh

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ABSTRACT

Adolescence is a transition period from childhood to adult life. During this period, pubertal development and sexual maturation take place. There is a substantial lacuna in the knowledge towards menstruation and menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls. Adolescent girls are often reluctant to discuss this topic with their parents, friends or anyone. This in turn leads to ignorance of the scientific facts and hygienic health practices among adolescent girls. Better knowledge and safe menstrual practices will avoid risk against reproductive tract infections and its consequences. With this scenario, it would be appropriate to give educational intervention to girls at school level itself. Therefore, increased knowledge about menstruation right from childhood may escalate safe practices and may help in mitigating the suffering of millions of women.

Objective: The study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among high school adolescent girls in selected schools of Damoh. Setting: The study was conducted in selected schools of Damoh.

Design: A pre experimental one group pre-test post-test design was used.

Sampling technique: The samples of this study are selected by using non probability non-probability purposive sampling technique.

Sample: The sample for present study comprises of 218 adolescent girls from selected high schools of Damoh.

Tools for data collection: The structured questionnaire was used as an instrument to measure the level of knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls.

Finding & Results: The finding of pre-test data Scores showed that majority 77% of adolescent girls had inadequate knowledge and 20% of the sample had moderate knowledge 3% had adequate knowledge. Findings of post-test data showed that majority 85% of the sample had adequate knowledge and 10% of the sample had moderate knowledge and 5% had inadequate knowledge. The mean post-test knowledge score (30.73) also was higher than the mean pre-test score (13.34). The comparison of pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of adolescent girls shows the obtained 't' value 35.72 is greater than the table value at 0.05 (2.32) level of significance. Therefore "t" value is found to be significant indicating that there is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge of adolescent girls.

Chi-square test was calculated to find out the association between the demographic variables and the level of knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls of selected high school adolescent girls of Damoh. The findings indicates that all the variables such as Age ($\chi^2 = 2.69$) Educational level ($\chi^2 = 5.45$), Religion ($\chi^2 = 10.57$) Family type ($\chi^2 = 6.91$), Mothers Education ($\chi^2 = 2.90$), Income of Family ($\chi^2 = 3.64$) Age of menarche ($\chi^2 = 2.35$), Source of information ($\chi^2 = 4.10$). Only in Religion, Family Type calculated $P < 0.01$ were found to be significant at 0.05 level of significance. Thus it can be interpreted that there is no significant association between pre-test levels of knowledge among adolescent girls with their selected demographic variables.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the PTP on Menstrual Hygiene was an effective method for providing moderate to adequate knowledge and help adolescent girls to adapt health life styles and to enable them to live a better quality of life by save guarding against the effects of poor Menstrual Hygiene.

Keywords: effectiveness, Knowledge, planned teaching programme, menstrual hygiene, and adolescent girls

1 Introduction

An adolescent belongs to a vital age group not only because they are "enterent Population" to parenthood but also because they are on the threshold between childhood and adulthood. As they attempt to cross this threshold they face various physiological, psychological and developmental changes [1]

Adolescence, the traditional period between childhoods

and adulthood, begins with puberty. Menstruation can be a first indication of puberty.[2]

Adolescence is regarded as a unique phase of human development. Among adolescent girl menarche is an important landmark in the process of growth and maturation. Though menstruation is a natural and normal physiological process for all healthy adult women as ever it has been surrounded by secrecy and myths in many societies.[3]

It is necessary to maintain healthy traditions, customs and healthy practices in the community and prevent harmful practices. Organization of education is essential as an agent of change after adequate training to bring about change regarding social customs, traditions and health seeking behaviour etc.,

The word puberty is derived from the Latin word, “puberties”, which means, “Age of manhood”. This is an overlapping period between the closing years of childhood and the beginning years of adolescence. This stage includes menstrual, emotional, social and physical maturity, and it is a stressful period. The girl experiences several problems during adolescence and menarche is one among them.

Though menstruation is a natural and normal physiological process for all healthy girls and women, it has been shrouded in myth and mystery in many societies. The silence and secrecy of menstruation, does not allow an open discussion on the subject.

Menstruation and menstrual practices are clouded by taboos and socio- cultural restrictions, even today, resulting in adolescent girls remaining ignorant of the scientific facts and hygienic health practices necessary for maintaining positive reproductive health. (Mandal 1994).[5]

Need of the Study

Approximately 19 % (1/5th) of the World’s population is in the age group of 10 – 19 years. As they are passing through a transitional period, from childhood to adulthood, they are undergoing a lot of physical as well as psychological stress, due to the changes taking place in their body.[1] Family members impose various restrictions on adolescent girls during menstruation regarding daily activities like taking cold drinks, play, exercises, worshipping etc., Girls are not confident about the self-care with regard to protection against staining of cloths during periods. They do not change the pads whenever it is soaked. A large number of the girls dispose their pads unhygienic ally that is throwing it as it is. In India; there are many myths, misconceptions as well as poor traditional practices, which compel them to practice certain menstrual practices, which are not hygienic as recommended. Thus, imparting knowledge about the menstrual hygiene practice may improve the usual practice by eliminating the obstacles to healthy practices.

A Planned Teaching Program on the felt need will be more suitable as it gives importance to the area where they lack knowledge.

Adolescent smoking behaviours, sources of tobacco, knowledge .The results of this study suggest that more financial and educational

2 Objectives

- To assess the existing knowledge of adolescent girls regarding menstrual hygiene.

- To conduct a Planned Teaching Program (PTP).
- To evaluate the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Program.
- To find out the association between the knowledge scores and selected demographic variables.

2.1 Hypothesis

H0₁ - There is no difference in knowledge from pre-test and post-test scores.

H0₂ - There is no significant association between the post-test scores and selected demographic variables..

2.2 Material and Methods

Research Design: One group pre-test post-test research design, which belongs to pre-experimental design, was selected for this study.

Setting: The study was conducted in selected high schools of Damoh

Population: The population selected for this study consisted of adolescent girls studying in selected high schools of Damoh

Sample: The sample size constitutes 218 adolescent girls, studying in selected high schools of Damoh .

Sampling Technique: The samples of this study were selected by using non probability purposive sampling technique.

Tool for data collection: The research tool was developed in English after an extensive of literature and experts opinion. A self-reported structured questionnaire was used for collection of data. Questionnaire is considered to be the most efficient and objective method which is quick and generally inexpensive means of obtaining data from large number of respondents.

Data analysis: The demographic variables were organized by using descriptive measures (frequency and percentage). The association between the level of knowledge and the selected demographic variables were assessed by chi-square test.

3 Finding and Results

3.1 Findings of demographic characteristics

Most of the subjects that is 103 (47.25 %) were of the age of 14 years and only 11 (5.05 %) were of the age of 12 years.

Majority of the subjects that is 92 (42.20 %) were studying IX standard and only 13 (5.96 %) were from X standard.

Most of the subjects that is 171 (78.44 %) were from Hindu background and only 2 (1 %) belong to other religion than Hindu, Muslim and Christian.

Among respondents, 143 (65.6 %) were from nuclear family and only 14 (6.42 %) were from extended family.

Among 218 respondents, 60 (27.5 %) of students’ mothers were educated up to higher secondary and only 19 (8.7 %) of students’ mothers had no formal education.

Among respondents, 72 (33 %) were having the family income above Rs. 4000/- per month and only 38 (17.4 %) were from the family where the income was between Rs. 2001 – Rs. 3000.

Majority of the subjects that is 93 (42.7 %) had attained menarche by 13 years of age where as only 19 (8.7 %) attained menarche at the age of 11 years. Among 218 respondents, 175 (80.3 %) had heard about Menstruation from the elders in the family. Among 218 respondents, 175 (80.3 %) had heard about Menstruation from the elders in the family.

3.2 Analysis of pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of adolescent girls regarding menstrual hygiene

The finding of pre-test data Scores showed that majority 77% of adolescent girls had inadequate knowledge and 20% of the sample had moderate knowledge 3% had adequate knowledge. Findings of post-test data showed that majority 85% of the sample had adequate knowledge and 10% of the sample had moderate knowledge and 5% had inadequate knowledge.(Fig No.1). The mean Post-test knowledge scores ($X_2 = 30.73$) was apparently higher than the mean Pre-test knowledge score ($X_1 = 13.34$).

3.3 Effectiveness of planned teaching program on knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls

Finding related to knowledge of adolescent girls regarding menstrual hygiene reveal that the Post-test knowledge scores ranged from 25 – 35 where as the Pre-test knowledge scores ranged from 2 – 21. The mean Post-test knowledge scores ($X_2 = 30.73$) was apparently higher than the mean Pre-test knowledge score ($X_1 = 13.34$). The median of Post-test knowledge score ($M_2 = 21.75$) was higher than the median of Pre-test knowledge score ($M_1 = 11.82$).The mean score was $30.72 \pm SD$ of the Post test was 5.64 and of mean score of pre test was $13.34 \pm SD$ of the pre test was 5.66.The mean difference was 27.39. There was significant increase in knowledge about menstrual hygiene with T value is 35.72* at $P < 0.05$ level. The comparison of pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of adolescent girls shows the obtained ‘t’ value 35.72 is greater than the table value at 0.05 (2.00) level of significance. Therefore “t” valve is found to be significant indicating that there is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge of adolescent girls.

Figure 1 over all Pre-test and Post-test mean knowledge scores on menstrual hygiene.

3.4 Association between Demographic variables and Pre and Post-test Knowledge level on menstrual hygiene

Chi-square test was calculated to find out the association between the demographic variables and the level of knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls of selected high school adolescent girls of Damoh. The findings indicates that all the variables such as Age ($\chi^2 = 2.69$) Educational level ($\chi^2 = 5.45$), Religion ($\chi^2 = 10.57$) Family type ($\chi^2 = 6.91$), Mothers Education ($\chi^2 = 2.90$), Income of Family ($\chi^2 = 3.64$) Age of menarche ($\chi^2 = 2.35$), Source of information ($\chi^2 = 4.10$) were found to be no significant at 0.05 level of significance. There was significant association found in religion, and family at 0.05 levels. Thus it can be interpreted that there is no significant association between pre-test levels of knowledge among adolescent girls with their selected demographic variables.

Table 1: Association between Post-test levels of knowledge with the selected Demographic variables N=218

S. No	Personal Characteristics	Below Median Score	Above Median Score	Chi-Square (χ^2)
1.	Age:			
	12 Years	5	6	2.69
	13 Years	43	24	d.f. = 3
	14 Years	57	48	P= 0.44
2.	Educational Status:			
	VII Standard	5	7	5.45
	VIII Standard	54	28	d.f. = 3
	IX Standard	62	47	P= 0.14
3.	Religion:			
	Hindu	88	59	10.57
	Muslim	16	25	d.f. = 2
	Christian	23	7	p < 0.01
4.	Type of family:			6.91
	Nuclear	81	73	d.f. = 1
	Joint/Extended	46	18	p < 0.01

4 Discussion

The problem stated is to find out the effectiveness of the Planned Teaching Program on Menstrual Hygiene among high school adolescent girls studying in selected schools at Damoh

Though Menstruation is a natural and Normal physiological process for all healthy girls and women, it has been shrouded in myth and mystery in many societies. Menstruation and related problems are not discussed by adolescents and their parents. If they have a thorough knowledge about Menstruation and Menstrual Hygiene most of the adolescent problems will be solved.

The present study conducted among adolescent girls found that most of the subjects 47.25 % were in the age group of 14 years and 5.05 % were of 12 years. This study was supported by Drakshayani Devi. K (1994) [6] who suggested that the girls should be educated about the significance of Menstruation and development of secondary sexual characteristics, selection of a sanitary Menstrual absorbent and its proper disposal.

This was supported by a study conducted by Mandal (1994) [5] on teaching adolescent school girls about Menstrual Hygiene with prepared information package used to teach a group of adolescent school girls with the sample size of 30 each in experimental and control group.

This study was aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of PTP on Menstrual Hygiene among high school adolescent girls studying in selected schools at Damoh. This was supported by George, who conducted a study to find out the effectiveness of a Planned Teaching Program on Menstrual Hygiene developed for pre adolescent girls in selected schools of Udupi districts by using one group pre-test, post-test control group design.[7] Nurses as women and competent professionals have a responsible to promote the right information and practices among women and girls.

In the present study, the mean post-test knowledge scores (30.73) of adolescent school girls were significantly higher than the mean pre-test knowledge scores (13.34), and the computed 't' value (35.72) is higher than the table value which shows the Planned Teaching Program was effective. This was supported by George (1999) who studied "the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Program on Menstrual Hygiene for pre-adolescent girls in selected schools of Udupi district". The study sample consisted of 32 each in experimental and control group. The findings reveal that following the teaching program the mean post-test knowledge scores (23.84) of experimental group was higher than the mean post-test knowledge scores the control group.

The PTP was found effective in increasing the knowledge of high school adolescent girls about Menstrual Hygiene. However administering PTP is not sufficient to enhance the knowledge, the repeated reinforcement is essential for understanding and application.

5 Conclusion

The present study assessed the knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls studying in high schools of Damoh and found that the majority of girls had inadequate knowledge related to menstrual hygiene. After planned teaching programme on menstrual hygiene there was significant improvement on knowledge of the adolescent girls regarding menstrual hygiene. The study concluded that the planned health education programme was effective in improving knowledge of adolescent girls regarding menstrual hygiene.

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